

The Psychological Resilience Scale (47 items)

Items	Never	Somehow	Always
No matter the obstacles, I can achieve my goals			
I make my own decisions and do not have them dictated to me by an external source			
I believe that the joy and excitement of life lies in the individual's ability to face its challenges			
The value of life lies in the individual's loyalty to certain principles and values			
When I make my future plans, I am often sure of my ability to implement them			
I attack problems to solve them and don't wait for them to happen			
Most of my lifetime is wasted in meaningless activities			
My success in matters (study, work, etc.) depended on my effort and not on luck or coincidence			
I have a curiosity and a desire to know what I don't know			
I believe that my life has a purpose and a meaning to live for			
Life is opportunities, not work and struggle			
I think an exciting life is one that has problems that I can address			
I have certain values and principles that I adhere to and maintain			
I believe that failure is due to reasons that lie within the person himself			
I have the ability to persevere when I finish solving any problem I face			
I have no goals to cling to or defend			
I think what often happens to me is the result of my planning			
Problems mobilize my strength and ability to challenge			
I do not hesitate to participate in any activity that serves the community in which I live			
There is actually no such thing as luck			
I feel afraid and threatened by the circumstances and events that may occur in my life			
I take the initiative to stand by others when they face any problem			
I believe that chance and luck play an important role in my life			
When I solve a problem, I find joy in moving on to solve another problem			
I think "being away from people is a spoilsport."			
I can control the course of my life			
I believe that facing problems tests my endurance and ability to persevere			

Taking care of myself doesn't leave me a chance to think about anything else			
I think bad luck is due to poor planning			
I have a love of adventure and a desire to explore my surroundings			
I take the initiative to do anything that I think will serve my family or community			
I believe that I have little influence on the events that happen to me			
I take the initiative to confront problems that I am confident in my ability to solve			
I care a lot about the issues and events going on around me			
I believe that individuals' lives are affected by external forces over which they have no control			
A monotonous life is an enjoyable life for me			
Life and everything in it is not worth living			
I believe in the saying, "Give me luck and throw me into the sea."			
I believe that a life without change is boring and routine			
I feel responsible towards others and take the initiative to help them.			
I believe that I have a strong influence on the events happening around me			
I feel afraid of life changes, as every change may involve a threat to me and my life			
I care about national issues and participate in them whenever possible.			
I plan my life's affairs and do not leave them to luck, chance, or external circumstances			
Change is the norm of life and what is important is the ability to face it successfully			
I change my values and principles whenever necessary			
Feel afraid to confront problems even before they happen			

Job Satisfaction Scale (43 items)

Items	Agree	Neutral	Disagree
I feel involved in important decision-making processes at my institution.			
My opinions are valued when decisions are made.			
I have adequate opportunities to contribute to institutional decisions.			
The decision-making process at my institution is transparent.			
I am regularly informed about decisions that affect my work.			
I believe the decision-making process at my institution is fair.			
I feel my role in decision-making is appropriate for my position.			
I am satisfied with my level of participation in institutional decisions.			
The distribution of teaching responsibilities is fair and balanced.			
I am satisfied with my teaching workload.			
There is flexibility in the allocation of teaching responsibilities.			
The process for assigning teaching duties is transparent.			
I feel supported in managing my teaching responsibilities.			
The teaching duties assigned to me align with my expertise.			
There is a good balance between teaching and other academic duties.			
Feedback on teaching performance is used effectively in assigning responsibilities.			
The criteria for teaching assignments are clear and consistent.			
I feel equipped to provide quality academic advising.			
The institution provides adequate resources for effective advising.			
Academic advising is valued and recognized as part of my role.			
The workload related to academic advising is manageable.			
I receive sufficient training and support for academic advising.			
The criteria for academic promotion are clear and attainable.			
The promotion process is fair and unbiased.			
I feel supported in my pursuit of academic promotion.			
I experience respectful interactions with my academic colleagues.			
The academic environment encourages positive interpersonal relations.			
I feel my contributions are respected by my peers.			
There is effective communication among academic staff.			
My work environment is conducive to productivity.			
I feel safe and secure in my workplace.			
The institution provides adequate facilities and resources for my work.			
I have a healthy work-life balance.			

The work environment is supportive and collegial.			
I am satisfied with the physical conditions of my workplace.			
The institution addresses concerns related to the work environment promptly.			
The work environment fosters professional growth.			
I am satisfied with my salary and compensation package.			
My compensation reflects my qualifications and experience.			
Benefits provided by the institution are adequate and satisfactory.			
Salary increments are fair and based on clear criteria.			
The compensation system is transparent and understandable.			
I feel financially rewarded for my contributions to the institution.			

Scientific Research Motivation Scale (24 items)

Items	always	sometimes	Never
I strive to achieve excellence in every research project I undertake.			
Completing a research project gives me a significant sense of accomplishment.			
I am motivated by the desire to contribute new knowledge in my field.			
Achieving research goals is a major driver of my professional activities.			
I feel personally satisfied when my research is recognized by peers.			
The success of my research projects is a key measure of my professional worth.			
I am constantly looking for ways to improve the quality of my research.			
Completing challenging research tasks is deeply rewarding for me.			
I aim to be recognized as a leader in my field.			
The thought of achieving a major breakthrough in my research excites me.			
I am always setting higher goals for my research endeavors.			
Being at the forefront of research developments is important to me.			
I actively seek opportunities for professional growth through my research.			
I am driven to undertake projects that have a significant impact.			
My career aspirations are strongly tied to my research achievements.			
I am motivated by the potential to advance in my academic career through research.			
I am energized by tackling difficult research problems.			
The more complex a research project, the more engaged I become.			
I prefer working on projects that push the boundaries of current knowledge.			
I see challenging research tasks as opportunities for learning and growth.			
Overcoming research obstacles is a highly motivating aspect of my work.			
I am not deterred by the possibility of failure in complex research projects.			
I actively seek out research projects that others might find too challenging.			

Solving difficult research problems is more satisfying than working on easier tasks.			
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